

ABC, it's as easy as 123 – or is it?

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Article first published in Farm North East (Ed: Gillanders, E.) Issue No: 113, October 2022

When the Jackson 5 sang “ABC, it's easy as 1 2 3” it's clear they hadn't envisaged the recently launched Scottish Government's (SG) Agriculture Bill Consultation (ABC). Like many across the industry, I was keen to see what was included in their consultation. I'll not dwell on the proposed tenancy reforms shoehorned into the Bill – other than to remind those of you that let land in, or out, to make sure you read the details and provide feedback to officials through your preferred route.

This Agriculture Bill is a necessary step in the move towards future support schemes. The proposed Bill will simply provide the necessary primary legislative framework to give the SG necessary powers to enable secondary legislation (e.g., regulations, Scottish Statutory Instruments) that will provide all the detail on how the different elements of the Agricultural Bill will operate in practice.

In the consultation the SG elaborates on the key outcomes the Bill intends to deliver. The Bill's objectives include that agricultural support should be more linked to: climate change; nature protection and restoration; high quality food production; wider rural development; animal health and welfare; and plant genetic resources and plant health. It is important to provide feedback on whether you agree, disagree or have any concerns about the relative balance of those objectives.

Further, the consultation explains that the Bill will establish four-tiers of support (a 'Base Level Direct Payment', an 'Enhanced Level Direct Payment', an 'Elective Payment' and 'Complementary Support'). It may be challenging to provide feedback on this model as the consultation does not discuss budget distribution across the Tiers, nor does it detail how these tiers might operate in practice, other than mention of a 'whole-farm plan'. Some of the suggested content of the 'whole farm plan' certainly took me by surprise.

To help consider what the future support system may look like I will stick my neck above the parapet and explain how I interpret Tiers 1 and 2 (Tier 3 looks to be a continuation of SRDP-type measures). Firstly, there is expectation that direct area-based direct support (like the BPS) will remain open to all eligible farmers/crofters (Tier 1), albeit with a smaller budget. This support may, however come with added requirements to complete a 'whole farm plan' and/or a carbon audit. It may also be possible that the SG adopt additional cross-compliance measures such as the EU's new GAEC 2 protecting wetlands and peatlands.

Secondly, SG aim to support those who deliver for nature protection and restoration and for climate change mitigation through a non-competitive scheme - the Tier 2 enhanced 'conditional' payment. Think of it like a more demanding greening scheme for all farms. The SG are currently considering a long menu of 'conditional' measures. The types of measures being considered fall under the following headings: Soil Management for GHG Emission Reduction; Improve Cultivated Soil Health; Crop Management for GHG Emission Reduction; Improving grassland and grazing management; Livestock Management for GHG Emission Reduction; Cattle feeding; Nutrient Management for GHG Emission Reduction; Maintain and Enhance Field Margins and other Permanent Habitats; Create New Nature Rich Habitats; Manage for Species found on Farmed Land; Woodland Creation and Management. As these measures are likely to evolve it is understandable that SG may be reticent to

share them publicly in case they set hares running in the wrong direction. However, I understand that the SG aim to test some of these measures through Track 2 of the National Test Programme.

How will this work? For me (remembering this is my opinion) we may end up with a Tier 2 menu of measures each with a bespoke weighting (like the existing Ecological Focus Area options) where you will need to combine measures to meet a threshold in order to be eligible for payment. That threshold may change over time to ensure a 'Just Transition' occurs. My preference (again it may be wrong) would be that the weightings for measures should be different for cropping land, permanent grassland and rough grazing – reflecting intensity of production and environmental priorities. Land based actions may, for example, include minimum or zero tillage methods, maintenance and enhancement of hedgerows/farm woodlands, undertaking integrated pest management, increased area of field headlands, reduced use of inorganic fertilisers / pesticides, provision of species rich grassland swards, beetle banks, flower meadows, use of precision farming techniques, improved habitat corridors, low emission slurry spreading, etc. Many of these measures contain activities that some land managers will already be doing to some extent. However, it is acknowledged that some may have a longer adaptation journey ahead to access Tier 2.

Within the consultation coupled support schemes and LFASS currently sit in Tier 4 – 'Complimentary Support'. Our coupled support is a direct payment and is intrinsically linked to our current BPS and Greening schemes, and therefore I believe should be included in Tiers 1 and 2 'Direct Payments'. The coupled schemes were established to compensate active farming in our grazing areas against high production costs that the 3-region BPS doesn't fully compensate for. LFASS acts in a similar vein – helping to maintain activity in many areas of Scotland. To me, our coupled support schemes are ideal vehicles for 'enhanced conditionality' that can also focus minds on minimising inefficiencies (and GHG emissions) in livestock systems. This could come in the form of use of single headline metrics – such as the calving interval of the dam of suckler calves, or ensuring calf and cow mortality rates remain below a maximum threshold – or even a composite metric of efficiency of all cattle in a business? These conditions can sharpen minds on many management aspects and there may be further encouragement of greater genetic selection for lower emissions, feed additives to reduce methane emissions, etc. Whilst these requirements may sound daunting, they may be the price the industry has to accept in order to maintain support in the long run.

Given the SG commitment to *"integrate enhanced conditionality of at least half of all funding for farming and crofting by 2025"* I believe that some of the things mentioned above may need to be added to existing schemes before the new scheme is launched. This can be done through adjusting existing coupled support scheme rules, greening rules and cross compliance rules. Given the economic pressures on farmers and crofters just now I hope that SG are selective in any such process and select measure that can either help reduce costs or improve efficiencies in the longer term.

Now is the time to engage. It is easy to ignore or disengage with the process, yet 6-months down the line you may find that *"you were consulted, and these objectives agreed"*. ABC, simple as 123? – certainly not!